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Investigating the Effects of Field-Trip-Based-Instruction On Biology Learning Outcomes: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

This study systematically reviewed researches that investigate the effects of field trips experiences on student's learning outcomes in biology. Peer-reviewed papers were searched using a variety of databases including (Google, Google scholar, Academia, Ask the public, conferences, journals, online library, and electronic journals). Using a protocol as bases of inclusion and exclusion. Any research article conducted on the effect of field trip on any of the students learning outcome variables (achievement, performance, retention, attitudes, motivation, and interest) in any Biology topic is considered. The inclusion criteria are that: only articles from 2009-2024 that examine the effect of field trip and any of the variables. Therefore any article before 2009 or did not study at least one of the variables was excluded. A total of 16 articles were selected and used for this study. The result indicates that field trip affects students learning outcomes In all the variables. The review suggests that all biology teachers should use field trip into their instruction, in order to improve student understanding of complex and abstract biology concepts.

Keywords; Field Trips, Biology Teaching, Students Learning Outcomes

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Introduction

Leaving the school premises is a social experience and one, which provides a change of tempo and scenery for students. School field trips are one of the basic elements in biology education and with the help of field trips students can learn biology, make observations in a better way and make learning more meaningful (Abdul, et al, 2015). Field-trip is a method of teaching that involves taking the students on an excursion outside the classroom for the purpose of making relevant observation necessary for understanding of the topic under study. Often times such trips/excursions enable student to obtain scientific, technological and vocational information (Akinbobola, et al, 2010). According to Ilori (2010), Field trips are aids that teacher uses to arouse the interest of the learner thereby enabling the learner to gain direct experience. Omeodu, et al, (2018) also pointed out that field trips exposes students to new experiences and can increase interest and engagement in science regardless of prior interest in a topic. However, during field trips, learners sharpen their skills of observations, perception and objective report of observations by utilizing all their senses Shakil, et al (2011).

Biology is a science of life concerned with the characteristics of living things, their forms, functions and relationship with one another and with their environment among others Bello, (2016). It is a unique branch of natural sciences, however, like other natural sciences; it is concerned with the search for in-depth understanding of natural phenomena and events Nnorom, (2015). Biology also remains to hold a distinctive place in the school curriculum. This is because the basic understanding of biology is required for study in a variety of disciplines such as Medicine, Agriculture, Pharmacy, Microbiology, Biochemistry, and Psychology, among others. It goes without saying that no student planning to pursue these courses of study can do without Biology. However, Due to immense benefits of the subject (Biology) to both individual and societal development, the federal government of Nigeria in the national policy on education, (2014). Made Biology a core Science subject at senior secondary school (SSS). The objectives of Biology programme are; i) adequate laboratory and field skills in biology ii) Meaningful and relevant knowledge in biology. iii) Ability to apply scientific knowledge in everyday Life in matters of personal and Community health and agriculture. iv) Reasonable functional scientific attitude and emphasis of content and context of syllabus is place on. v) Field study guide discovery/ Biology as inquiry Thus from the above objectives, an outdoor strategy such as field trip has been recommended

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by FME for its implementation for accomplishments of Biology objectives in the secondary School in Nigeria.

Many systematic literature review were conducted in the field trip and students learning. Some of the reviews carried out by previous researchers include; a review of research in the field trip and their value in education which examine the importance of science field trips and educational tools to connects the students to classroom concepts (Behrendt, et al 2014). Also, Cathryn (2010), conducted a systematic review on the use and implementation of science field trips. Relatedly, Prather (1989) systematically reviewed the value of field trip in science instruction. These reviews channel effort toward examining the impact of field trip in promoting student learning.

However, despite the effort put by previous reviews, intensive review of the existing literature revealed no systematic review was carried out specifically on investigating the effect of field trips based instruction in biology learning outcomes. Also, the reviews conducted by previous reviewers did not involve major parameter that shows methodology and the actual processes the researchers follow in their empirical researches.

This review therefore, aim at retrieving the empirical studies carried out on effect of field trips based instruction strategy with reference to biology only covering a period of 15 years (2009-2024) to enable the researcher include all accessible and relevant articles published on impact factor journals. It will also enable the researcher to present a comprehensive outlook on the literature and state of art about field trip and learning of biology.

Research objectives

1. To determine the distribution of research on field trips in biology by country and educational level.
2. To identify the research designs and instruments used to assess the impact of field trips on biology learning outcomes.
3. To describe the different learning outcome examined by the researchers when assessing the impact of field trips on biology learning.
4. To identify the key limitations found in research reviewed on field trips in biology learning

Research Questions

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In the most specific terms, the review answered the following research questions:

1. What is the distribution of research on field trip in biology by country, and by educational level?
2. What research design and instruments were used by researchers in assessing field trip on students learning outcomes in biology?
3. What are the learning outcomes examine by researchers in assessing field trip on students learning outcomes in biology?
4. What are the limitations of the researches reviewed on field trips in biology learning?

Methodology

The review searched relevant literature using keywords “field trip”, “field trip and biology”, “field trip in biology and achievement”, “field trip in biology and performance”, “field trip in biology and interest”, “field trip in biology and Retention,” “field trip in biology and attitude”, “field in biology and motivation. The search engine and database used include: goggle, goggle scholar, research gate, ask the public, ERIC, E-library, journals, conference and electronic journal. The result of these was 102 articles.

Study Selection

The selected study were limited to students learning outcomes (performance, achievement, attitude, motivation, interest, retention) in biology which brought the no of article to 61, the duration was restricted to fifteen years from 2009 to 2024 .see fig 1.this cut down the no of article to 20. Therefore, any study before 2009 is excluded.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria were place to make sure that the selected studies were relevant and appropriate to answer the questions. Table 1 below described the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

<u>Inclusion criteria</u>	<u>Exclusion criteria</u>
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1. Full text article.	Incomplete article.
2. Any studies conducted from 2009 to 2024.	Studies conducted before 2009.
3. Manuscripts written in English	Any other language other than English.
4. Reference journals	Non reference journals, articles, books, thesis
5. Studies on field trip and any of performance, achievement, motivation, retention, interest or attitude in biology.	Studies not include field trip and any other variables from inclusion criteria.

Source (field work, 2025)

After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total number of 20 articles were found to be suitable for inclusion in this review. The articles were analyzed in and discussed in accordance with the research questions.

Framework Analysis

The framework of the results from the review was tabulated using thirteen items/element and used as data for analysis, discussions of findings. The items are Serial number, Author, Year. Title, Type of Publication, Location, Knowledge Domain, Educational level, Methodology, Sample, Instrument, Independent variables, Limitation, and findings

Quality Assessment

To get an authentic and qualitative data about the effects of field trips on learning outcomes only complete and full text available articles published in peer review journal were selected and reviewed. The journals were mostly from reputable ones. Therefore the findings from these articles are expected to be of high accuracy and precision.

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S/N	Author	Year	Location	Title	Knowledge Domain	level	Methodology	Sample	In
1	Egwu, S.O & Okigbo, E.C	2021	Nigeria	Effect of field trip on secondary school students achievement in ecology in Anambra state	Ecology	Sec. sch.	Quasi Experimental	148	BA Te
2	Ezechi, N.G.	2018	Nigeria	Influence of field trip in teaching and learning of biology	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Survey Design	100	Quest
3	Ugwu, C.B.A.		Nigeria	Enhancing student's interest and achievement in senior secondary school in biology through field trip teaching approach	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	100	Test
4	Shuvra, D.			Effect of field trip on students' academic performance in biology	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	200	Test
5	Nnenna, G.E.		Nigeria	Field trips; A viable tool for students Achievement in biology	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Survey Design	391	Quest
6	Sandip, M.		India	Attitude towards field excursion in biological science and achievement at higher secondary school	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Survey Design	289	Test
7	Mahmud, et al.	2022	Nigeria	Impact of field trip on the retention and academic performance in ecology, among sec. sch. Students I zaria, kaduna state.	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	200	Test
8	Bwanhot, E.S.	2021	Nigeria	Impact of field trip on academic performance of secondary school students in ecology concept in kaduna state.	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Experimental Design		Test
9	Zumyil, C.F., & Toma, M.A.	2022	Nigeria	Effect of field trip instructional strategies on students interest and achievement in ecology in plateau central zone, Nigeria.	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	106	Test
10	Obineke, C.J &		Nigeria	Effect of two modes of field trip method on students' achievement in senior secondary school in ecology in Nsukka local government area, enugu state	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	120	Test
11	Gormez, I.	2014	Turkey	Effect of field trip oriented instruction on ninth grade in students' achievement in animal diversity unit, continuing and academic motivation	Animal diversity	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	87	Test
12	Ajaja, O.P	2010		Effect of field trip on learning outcome In biology	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Experimental Design	100	Test
13	Anita, et al.	2018	Indonesia	The influence of field trip on high school students scientific literacy and attitude towards science in ecosystem concept	Ecosystem	University			
14	Usman, A.	2020	Nigeria	Effect of field trip instructional strategy on	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	71	Test &

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15	Denen, D. U. & Isah, S.A.	2019	Nigeria	students interest in ecology in nasarawa state, Nigeria. Effect of field trip instructional strategy on ss1 student interest and achievement in ecological concept in dutsin-ma LGA katsina state	Ecological concepts	Sec. Sch.	Quasi experimental	82	test
16	Nurhasnah, N., et al.	2019	Indonesia	Effectiveness of field trip in biology towards students increased concern for biodiversity Values	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi experiment	96	Test

Source (field work, 2024)

Research Question One; what is the distribution of research on field trip in biology by country, educational level and the knowledge domain?

Table 3, 4, and 5 presented the distribution of research on field trip in biology by country, educational level and the knowledge domain respectively.

Table 3: Frequency of the studies by countries

Country	Frequency (f)	Studies
Nigeria	12	[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[7],[8],[9],[10],[12],[14],[15]
India	1	[6]
Indonesia	2	[13],[16]
Turkey	1	[1]

Source (field work, 2024)

Table 3: indicated to a total of four countries where the empirical studies were carried out were involved in the review. Nigeria recorded the highest frequency of twelve (12) studies

Figure 2: Distribution of Field Trip Researches in Biology by Country

Table 4: Frequency of Studies by Educational Level

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Educational level	Frequency	Studies
Secondary	15	
University	1	

Of the 16 articles reviewed, 15 studies were conducted with secondary school biology students as the participants while 1 study were conducted with university students

Research Question Two; what research design and instruments were used by researchers in assessing field trip on students learning outcomes in biology?

Table 5: Frequency of Studies by Research Design

Research design	Frequency	Studies
Quasi experimental design	11	[2][5][6][8][12]
Experimental design	2	[8][12]
Survey	3	[2][5][5]

of the table above, 11 articles uses quasi experimental design, 3 uses survey while 2 uses experimental design.

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Table 6: Frequency of Studies By instruments

Instrument	Frequency	Studies
Test	14	[2], [5]
Questionnaire	2	[2],

The table above indicates that almost all the empirical studies reviewed uses test as their instruments for data collection.

Research Question Three; what are the learning outcomes examine by researchers in assessing field trip on students learning outcomes in biology?

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Table 7: Frequency of Studies by Learning Outcomes

Learning Outcomes Measured	Frequency	Studies
Achievement	8	[1][3][5][6][9][10][11][14][15]
Performance	4	[2][4][7][8]
Interest	4	[3][14][15][16]
Motivation	2	[11][16]
Retention	1	[7]
Attitude	2	[12][13]

Of the table above the result indicates that the learning outcomes achievement has the highest frequency of 8 studies, followed by interest and performance with 4-4 studies, motivation and attitudes has 2-2 while retention has only 1 study.

Research Question Three; what are the limitations of the studies?

Study	Limitation
1.	Carried out in one region , Focuses only on one topic
2.	Small sample size, Conducted in a region, Focuses only on one topic
3.	Small sample size, Limited scope Conducted in one region
4.	Focuses only on one topic
5.	Conducted in one region
6.	Limited scope, Focuses only on one topic
7.	Conducted in one region; Focuses only on one topic
8.	Sample size is too small, Conducted in one region
9.	Small sample size, Focuses only on one topic
10.	Conducted in one region Focus in only one topic
11.	Small sample size, conducted in one region, focuses only on one topic
12.	Small sample size, captured only one region, focuses only on one topic
13.	Small sample size carried out in one region, focuses only on one topic
14.	Small sample size, restricted in one region
15.	Small sample size, carried out in one region
16.	Limited scope

Source (field work, 2024)

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Discussion of findings

The findings of this systematic review were discussed based on research questions. The 16 peer-reviewed articles, demonstrates a notable concentration of research on field trips within the Nigerian educational context, particularly at secondary school level. Methodologically, the reviewed studies exhibit a preference for quasi-experimental designs and test instruments. The primary learning outcomes investigated were cognitive in nature, specifically academic achievement and knowledge retention.

Conclusion:

This systematic review reveals a strong positive association between field trips based-instructions and several biology learning outcomes. Consistent findings indicate that field trips can significantly increase student academic achievements, improve students' knowledge retention, interest, performance, motivation, and student's attitude towards learning biology. Furthermore a significant portion of the reviewed studies was conducted in secondary school setting, limiting the generality of findings to university students. Additionally, Limited research beyond Nigeria and secondary schools, along with the need for more methodologies, more than just test scores, and a broader assessment of learning outcomes shows clear directions for future research on field trips.

Suggestions for Further Studies:

1. All biology teachers should use field trip into their instruction, in order to improve student understanding of complex and abstract biology concepts.
2. Future research should prioritize conducting studies in university settings, research designs other than quasi experimental and test scores for instrumentation.

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